

Self-Efficacy and Self-Belief in Mathematics and Access Student Progression

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This study examined the relationship between Access students' general self-efficacy, their beliefs about their mathematics abilities, the level of mathematics module they choose and their progression to higher education. An explanatory, sequential mixed methods approach was adopted for the study, which took place over three academic years, 2017/18, 2018/19 and 2019/20. During the study, questionnaires were completed by 184 students in the Access programme at Technological University Dublin and 24 students participated in interviews. All Access students must complete a module in advanced, intermediate or fundamental mathematics. Results revealed that students with higher belief in their mathematics ability were more likely to study advanced mathematics and more likely to pass mathematics modules. Students studying intermediate mathematics were most likely to progress to higher education, and non-Irish nationals, who had higher belief in their mathematics abilities than Irish nationals, were less likely to progress in advanced mathematics than their peers. Recommendations for improving students' belief in their mathematics ability and progression are provided.

Introduction

Access programmes provide students from backgrounds with little tradition of participating in higher education with an opportunity to access and progress in undergraduate studies (Technological University Dublin, 2020). However, there is little research on Access student progression. The goal of this study is to examine the relationship, if any, between Access students' general self-efficacy (GSE), their beliefs about their mathematics abilities (BMA), the level of mathematics module they choose and their progression to higher education.

Mathematics in Higher Education

Research has highlighted the importance of mathematics skills in education and in society (Wismath & Warrell, 2015). Mathematics is relevant in "high-status careers," particularly those in the high-technology sector (Ma & Johnson, 2008). Additionally, teaching students to use logic and reasoning enables them to develop critical thinking skills and to extend mathematical methods to other disciplines (Hodge, 2003). However, mathematics education can discriminate against and exclude some students due to lack of resources, racism, sexism, language deficiencies and a form of elitism where students are differentiated based on 'ability' (Skovsmose, 2004).

Irish students' performance in mathematics in the Leaving Certificate, the terminal examination for Irish secondary school students, can predict a student's performance in all academic disciplines (Hyland, 2011). Additionally, there is a strong link between performance in mathematics in the Leaving Certificate and successful progression to second year in higher education (Bergin & Reilly, 2005; Mooney et al., 2010; O'Shea, 2021).

Although mathematics skills have been shown to benefit students, over time, there has been a decline in higher education students' basic mathematics competencies that has become known as the "mathematics problem" (Hawkes & Savage, 1999; Faulkner, 2012).

Additionally, higher education students commonly admit that they do not like mathematics, or they are "no good at mathematics" (Ryan & Fitzmaurice, 2017, p. 49). According to Marshall et al. (2017), students' negative experiences with mathematics in the past can result in avoidance and procrastination behaviours that affect students' course choices, their self-efficacy and their progression in higher education. Lopez and Lent (1992) found that prior performance was the most efficient predictor of high school students' self-efficacy in mathematics, and Hall and Panton (2005) found that students with more self-belief about their ability to succeed in higher education mathematics classes also had better mathematical skills.

There is a lack of research on Access student progression. However, the findings related to higher education students outlined above may also be relevant to Access students.

The Access Programme at Technological University Dublin

The Access programme at Technological University Dublin (TU Dublin) is a one-year programme offering an alternative route to higher education for mature students, and for young adults who are socio-economically disadvantaged (Technological University Dublin, 2020). In Ireland, mature students are 23 years or older on January 1 of the year they enter higher education and young adults are aged 22 years and under. All Access students must study one mathematics module each semester at fundamental, intermediate or advanced level.

This study is part of a larger study on the factors affecting the progression of Access students to undergraduate studies. A subset of the data from the larger study is provided here. The larger study revealed that demographic, psychosocial, educational, environmental and institutional factors affect Access student progression. The current study focuses on the effect of GSE and BMA on students' mathematical experiences in Access education and their progression to undergraduate studies. It aimed to answer the following research question:

Is there a relationship between Access students' GSE and BMA and (a) the level of mathematics they study and (b) their progression to higher education?

Method

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the ethics committee at TU Dublin. An explanatory, sequential mixed methods approach was adopted for the study, which took place over three academic years, 2017/18, 2018/19 and 2019/20. During the quantitative phase of the research, Access students completed a 29-item questionnaire at the start of the academic year. This questionnaire included the General Self-Efficacy Scale (Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1995), which assesses ability to deal with unusual or difficult situations and was used to measure Access students' GSE. The scale includes 10-items with a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 'not at all true' to 'exactly true'. Additionally, students rated their BMA using a five-point Likert scale, where 1 represented 'excellent' and 5 represented 'poor'.

Although the questionnaire also included questions related to personality, motivation and relatedness, the focus of the current paper is self-efficacy, self-belief and progression.

Progression was measured based on whether students were offered a place at a higher education institution or not. The data was analysed using SPSS. Spearman's correlation (ρ), Mann-Whitney U tests (U) and Chi square tests (χ^2) were conducted. For all Chi-square tests, dichotomous variables were used. For example, to determine whether there was an association between gender and GSE score, female was coded as 1, male was coded as 2, GSE score below the median was coded as 1 and GSE score above the median was coded as 2.

During the qualitative phase of the research, 24 students who had completed a questionnaire at the start of the academic year participated in a one-to-one, semi-structured interview with the researcher before completing their final examinations. Interview participants included male, female, young adult, mature, Irish national and non-Irish national students. Interviews were approximately 30 minutes in duration and were transcribed and coded using the grounded theory approach outlined by Strauss and Corbin (1990).

Results

Questionnaires were completed by 184 students over the three years of the study. In all, 85% of students who studied foundation mathematics, 84% of those who studied intermediate mathematics and 89% of students who studied advanced mathematics progressed to higher education. Participant demographics are outlined in Table 1.

Table 1

Percentage of Access Students Studying Fundamental, Intermediate and Advanced Mathematics by Age, Gender and Nationality

	Fundamental Mathematics	Intermediate Mathematics	Advanced Mathematics
% enrolled	25%	64%	11%
Mature	30%	62%	8%
Young Adult	19%	66%	15%
Male	26%	59%	15%
Female	24%	70%	6%
Irish National	29%	61%	10%
Non-Irish National	18%	70%	12%

Results revealed that there was a weak positive correlation between Access students' GSE and their BMA ($\rho(169) = .215, p = .005$). Students with higher GSE scores (scores above the median) had higher BMA than those with lower GSE scores (scores below the median). Moreover, students with higher GSE scores were significantly more likely to rate their BMA as above average or excellent compared to those with low GSE ($\chi^2 = 8.00, df = 1, p = .018$).

Findings showed that there was a statistically significant relationship between students' GSE and the level of mathematics they studied. Students with lower GSE scores were significantly more likely to study fundamental mathematics than their peers ($\chi^2 = 6.25, df = 1, p = .012$). There was also a statistically significant relationship between students' BMA and the level of mathematics they studied. Students who rated their BMA as above

average or excellent were significantly more likely to study advanced mathematics than students who rated their BMA as below average or poor ($\chi^2 = 10.06$, $df = 1$, $p = .007$). Moreover, students who rated their BMA as excellent or above average were significantly more likely to pass their mathematics module (receive a total of 40% or more) than those who rated their BMA as average, below average or poor ($\chi^2 = 12.41$, $df = 1$, $p = .002$).

Male and female students did not differ in their GSE scores ($\chi^2 = 1.71$, $df = 1$, $p = .19$) or their BMA ($\chi^2 = 2.34$, $df = 1$, $p = .310$) but males were significantly more likely to study advanced mathematics ($\chi^2 = 3.75$, $df = 1$, $p = .053$). Additionally, non-Irish nationals had significantly higher BMA scores than their Irish peers ($\chi^2 = 12.78$, $df = 1$, $p = .002$) and significantly higher GSE scores ($\chi^2 = 8.18$, $df = 1$, $p = .004$). They were also more likely to study advanced mathematics or intermediate mathematics than Irish nationals ($\chi^2 = 3.58$, $df = 1$, $p = .059$). There was no significant difference in GSE ($\chi^2 = .174$, $df = 1$, $p = .677$) or BMA ($\chi^2 = 1.88$, $df = 1$, $p = .390$) scores between young adults and mature students.

Mathematics and Progression

Overall, there was no statistically significant difference in progression based on Access students' mean rank for GSE ($U = 2815.5$, $p = .425$) or their BMA ($\chi^2 = 3.84$, $df = 1$, $p = .146$). However, students studying intermediate mathematics were more likely to progress to higher education ($\chi^2 = 7.57$, $df = 1$, $p = .006$) than those studying fundamental or advanced mathematics. They were also significantly more likely to have higher GSE scores ($\chi^2 = 4.38$, $df = 1$, $p = .036$) and higher BMA scores ($\chi^2 = 4.70$, $df = 1$, $p = .096$) than their peers. Mature students studying intermediate mathematics were more likely to progress than their young adult peers ($\chi^2 = 8.39$, $df = 1$, $p = .004$). Non-Irish nationals who studied advanced mathematics had lower progression rates than Irish nationals ($\chi^2 = 2.92$, $df = 1$, $p = .087$).

Qualitative Findings

In interviews, students contended that 'confidence' was important in progression. Lack of 'confidence' was mentioned by 11 interviewees (46%) as a problem for students who failed to progress. One interviewee, Dylan (male/mature/Irish national), recalled that a student who lacked BMA failed to progress. A second interviewee, Oscar (male/mature/Irish national), explained that he sometimes questioned whether he should continue with his studies.

'Overconfidence' was seen as a barrier to the progression of Access students also. Dylan explained that one student set his targets too high and failed to progress. He felt that this student chose the most demanding modules and could not keep up, leading to the student's departure from the programme.

Interviewees noted that Access students chose the level of their mathematics module depending on their BMA. Two interviewees, Oscar and Olena (female/Irish/young adult), noted that they chose to study fundamental mathematics because they lacked BMA. Oscar wanted to study media in higher education but changed his mind when he realised that he

would be required to study intermediate or advanced mathematics. Alan (male/young adult/non-Irish national) noted that some Access students did not like mathematics.

Interviewees contended that mature students were more focused on their studies than young adults. However, they noted that both mature students and young adults engaged in informal learning communities that provided mathematics support.

Kassie (female/mature/non-Irish national), Tammy (female/young adult/non-Irish national) and James (male/young adult/non-Irish national) felt that English language difficulties affected their performance in some modules. Although non-Irish nationals may not have experienced language difficulties in mathematics, other modules may have been more difficult, particularly those that involved multiple choice questions.

Discussion

This study aimed to determine whether Access students' BMA and GSE affected the level of mathematics they study and their progression to undergraduate studies. Findings revealed that students who rated their BMA as above average or excellent were significantly more likely to study advanced mathematics than those who rated their BMA as average or below average. This may be because Access students with higher BMA have better mathematical skills or because their past performance in mathematics affected their BMA as indicated by Lopez and Lent (1992). Interviewees concurred that most Access students chose the level of their mathematics module depending on their BMA, particularly students studying fundamental mathematics. They contended that Access students commonly admit that they do not like or are "not good" at mathematics.

Students who rated their BMA as above average or excellent were significantly more likely to pass their mathematics module than students who rated their BMA as average, below average or poor. Wesson and Derrer-Rendall (2011) found that students generally have a good awareness of their academic abilities and House (2000) found that academic background and students' BMA are significantly related to the grades they achieve in mathematics courses in higher education. However, both quantitative and qualitative findings in the current study suggest that some students may have overrated their ability in mathematics.

Non-Irish nationals had higher BMA than Irish nationals. However, non-Irish nationals who studied advanced mathematics were significantly less likely to progress to higher education than their peers. Although non-native speakers of English in the advanced mathematics programme did not fail their mathematics module, interviewees noted that they may have failed to progress because they experienced difficulties in modules that required advanced English language skills. English competency can affect higher education students' academic achievement (Harris & Ní Chonaill, 2016; Paton, 2007).

Quantitative findings also revealed that mature students who studied intermediate mathematics were significantly more likely to progress to higher education than young adults. Interviewees explained this, noting that mature students may be more likely to progress because they put more effort into their studies than young adults. Mature students do better

than their younger counterparts in higher education also (Faulkner et al. 2016; Hoskins et al., 1997).

According to interviewees, low BMA may have affected the progression of some students to undergraduate studies as students felt that they were not good at mathematics or could not engage in the mathematics module and left the Access programme as a result.

Conclusion

The findings from the current study reveal the importance of having positive BMA and higher GSE scores. Access students with higher BMA and higher GSE were more likely to study advanced mathematics and more likely to pass mathematics overall. However, it is important that students are not overconfident as this may result in failure to progress.

These findings indicate the importance of improving students' BMA and their GSE. Access students can be encouraged to improve their BMA if lecturers follow Heslin and Kelhe's (2006) recommendations for improving self-belief. This would involve engaging students in enactive self-mastery, which is achieved when people master at least part of a task; role-modelling, which involves watching someone else perform a task and forming ideas about how the task can be performed; and verbal persuasion, which involves positive self-talk or encouragement and praise from an educator. Moreover, Access students should be encouraged to monitor their understanding and progress in learning by adopting effective study strategies and see intelligence as a malleable quality. Ehrlinger and Shain (2014) found that these factors encourage accuracy in self-belief. Similar results have been found with higher education students, however, this is not something which has been examined objectively in longitudinal research where Access students are concerned so it is important to build up this knowledge base in a scientific way. This study goes some way to doing that.

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